

NATIONAL GENE BANK OF AGRICULTURAL CROPS OF UZBEKISTAN: CONSERVATION, PROSPECTS, AND EFFICIENT USE

Kh.M. Khasanov

Head of the National Gene Bank, Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the current status, significance, and development prospects of the National Gene Bank of agricultural crops of Uzbekistan. It examines the role of the gene bank in conserving plant genetic resources, identifies existing problems and their potential solutions and explores opportunities for efficient utilization of the gene pool based on advanced international experiences. The study proposes recommendations for developing the gene bank and ensuring the effective use of genetic resources.*

Keywords: *gene bank, plant genetic resources, conservation, productivity, breeding, genetic passport, biotechnology.*

Introduction

One of the most pressing issues facing modern global agriculture is ensuring food security. This challenge is further exacerbated by factors such as rapid population growth, climate change, and the limited availability of land and water resources. In this context, it is of utmost importance to increase the productivity of agricultural crops and develop varieties resistant to diseases, pests, and adverse environmental conditions.

Plant genetic resources (PGR) are a primary source for the development of food and agriculture. They ensure the genetic diversity of crops, allowing for the identification and utilization of valuable genes in breeding programs. Conservation and rational use of PGR not only contribute to food security but also serve to preserve biodiversity, promote ecological balance, and foster the sustainable development of agriculture.

Worldwide, extensive efforts are being undertaken to conserve and utilize PGR. International organizations such as the FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations) and CGIAR (Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research) are implementing programs to support the conservation, characterization, utilization, and exchange of genetic resources. The International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (ITPGRFA), adopted in 2004, is a critical legal framework for international cooperation in the conservation and utilization of PGR [8].

Agriculture is a key sector of the Uzbek economy. The country cultivates cotton, cereals, fruits, vegetables, and other agricultural crops. Uzbekistan's climatic conditions provide favorable opportunities for growing a wide variety of crops. However, issues such as water scarcity, soil salinization, and the spread of diseases and pests are significantly impacting agriculture.

In this situation, the conservation and efficient use of PGR in Uzbekistan are of paramount importance. The National Gene Bank operates in the country, housing genetic collections of various crops. However, addressing a number of challenges is necessary for the effective utilization of gene bank resources. These include characterizing the gene pool using modern

methods, creating a genetic passport for each sample, and employing molecular markers to accelerate the breeding process.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the state of PGR conservation and efficient use in Uzbekistan, to identify existing problems, and to develop scientifically-grounded recommendations for addressing them. The study examines the activities of the National Gene Bank of Uzbekistan, the composition of genetic collections, the level of characterization, and the possibilities for use in breeding. It also reviews international experiences in PGR conservation and utilization and identifies methods suitable for Uzbekistan's conditions. The results of this study will contribute to the development of agriculture in Uzbekistan, ensuring food security and increasing export potential.

Literature Review

The conservation and rational use of plant genetic resources (PGR) is a globally significant task. Researchers worldwide are conducting extensive studies in this area. For example, the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) report, "The State of the World's Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture," [1] provides an in-depth analysis of the importance of PGR and the challenges associated with their conservation and utilization.

Hoxie [2] examines the role of gene banks in conserving PGR, with particular attention to the challenges in the post-Nagoya Protocol era. The study emphasizes the role of gene banks in Access and Benefit Sharing (ABS) of genetic resources and the importance of international cooperation. Ford-Lloyd and Jackson [3] provide a detailed analysis of seed conservation methods in gene banks, demonstrating that genetic diversity can be preserved through the use of effective conservation methods. They studied the effects of factors such as the physiological condition, moisture content, and temperature of seeds on their shelf life.

Aitken et al. [4] studied the possibilities of using genetic resources from gene banks in breeding, showing that using wild relatives in breeding can increase the productivity of crops such as sugar beets. The use of molecular markers helps to speed up the breeding process. Rao et al. [5] also published a manual on working with seeds in gene banks, providing recommendations for collecting, cleaning, drying, storing, and assessing the quality of seeds. Engelmann [6] highlights methods of cryopreservation of plant genetic resources, in particular the advantages of storage in liquid nitrogen. Cryopreservation is the most effective method for long-term storage of vegetatively propagated crops and seeds.

In addition, a number of studies have been conducted in Uzbekistan on the conservation and utilization of PGR. In particular, scientists at the Research Institute of Plant Industry are working on the use of gene bank resources to create new varieties of crops adapted to the conditions of Uzbekistan [7].

Types of Gene Banks

Gene banks designed to conserve plant genetic resources are divided into several types according to the duration of storage by their conservation period:

- Short-term gene bank (working collection) - germination is maintained for 3-7 years, depending on the type of crop, in normal room conditions (20-22°C).
- Medium-term gene bank - stored in special cold stores (+4°C) for up to 15-20 years.
- Long-term gene bank - stored in special cold stores (-18°C) for 100 years or more [5].

Field gene banks and cryoconservation methods are used for vegetatively propagated crops [6].

National Gene Bank of Uzbekistan

Uzbekistan has a "National Gene Bank" for the conservation of PGR, which is located at the Uzbek Research Institute of Plant Industry. It houses medium- and short-term seed gene banks and a field gene bank. Short-term gene banks are also available at breeding institutions throughout the country. The National Gene Bank stores seeds and field gene banks containing 21,969 samples of field crops, 12,969 samples of industrial crops, 5,755 samples of vegetable and melon crops, 5,002 samples of fruit crops and grapes, for a total of more than 45,000 samples of 103 agricultural crops are stored alive in seed and field gene banks. A total of more than 85,000 samples are stored in all scientific institutions throughout the country, which puts Uzbekistan in 14th place in the world and 2nd place in the CIS countries after Russia. The National Gene Bank cooperates with international gene banks ICARDA, CIMMYT, ICRISAT, the Vegetable Center, and gene banks in countries such as Korea, Germany, Russia, and Turkey.

Measures to Develop the National Gene Bank

In accordance with the Decree No. PQ-4803 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 11, 2020, it is planned to carry out a major renovation of the National Gene Bank building and create long-term storage facilities within the framework of the project "Modernization of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan". USD 400,000 has been allocated for this work. At a meeting held on July 17 under the chairmanship of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, it was instructed to develop measures to expand the gene bank of crops, and USD 24 million will be allocated for these works.

Discussion

In our republic, attention should be paid to varieties, their seed production, and the application of correct agronomy in order to increase the productivity of agricultural crops. In order to increase exports, it is necessary to create our own new varieties adapted to local conditions. Currently, the import of seeds of most crops into our republic indicates the need to develop breeding efforts.

The conservation and use of PGR in breeding is important for the development of agriculture in Uzbekistan. At a time when problems such as global climate change, water scarcity, and disease spread are seriously affecting agriculture, the role of PGR is increasing. The genetic diversity stored in the National Gene Bank is a valuable resource for Uzbek breeders. However, in order to efficiently use gene bank resources, a number of problems need to be solved. In particular, characterizing the gene pool with modern methods, creating a genetic passport for each sample, and using molecular markers will help to speed up the breeding process.

At the Scientific Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources, work has already begun on creating new cultivars through accelerated breeding techniques, using advanced biotechnological approaches and materials from the National Genebank. In addition, researchers at the Institute, in collaboration with **Xinjiang Jiuyu Agricultural Development** (China), have initiated programs aimed at producing hybrid maize seeds to substitute imported hybrids. Breeding efforts are also underway to develop hybrid varieties of maize, sunflower, and vegetable crops that are well adapted to local agro-climatic conditions. Such projects will significantly contribute to strengthening national plant breeding and reducing dependence on imports.

Conclusions and Recommendations

In order to further develop the conservation and effective utilization of plant genetic resources (PGR) in Uzbekistan, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Strengthening the National Genebank:** Include the National Genebank in the list of "unique national objects," ensure its financial independence, and introduce modern methods of

germplasm conservation (cryopreservation, *in vitro* conservation). Provide sustainable funding for necessary agrotechnical measures for the maintenance and regeneration of accessions in field genebanks.

2. **Molecular Characterization of Germplasm:** Characterize germplasm at the molecular level using modern biotechnological tools and create a genetic passport for each accession. Genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics should be integrated to achieve a comprehensive understanding of the genetic resources.

3. **Establishing a National Coordination Center:** Create a coordination center for plant genetic resources in Uzbekistan. This center will unify germplasm collections from all national institutions under the National Genebank, establish and manage an electronic database, coordinate scientific research, foster international collaboration, and support human capacity development in the field of PGR.

4. **Strengthening Collaboration Between Breeding Institutions and the Genebank:** Enhance cooperation between the National Genebank and breeding institutions to promote the wide use of germplasm in breeding programs. Special attention should be given to utilizing accessions with genes conferring resistance to diseases, pests, and adverse climatic conditions when creating new cultivars.

5. **Human Capacity Development:** Improve the system for training specialists in PGR management and plant breeding. Send young scientists for internships at foreign research centers, and ensure their participation in international conferences and workshops.

Implementation of these recommendations will contribute to the sustainable development of agriculture in Uzbekistan, strengthen food security, and increase export potential. Moreover, improving the national seed system—particularly through the development of private seed enterprises and the enhancement of seed quality control mechanisms—is essential. In this regard, adopting and adapting the best practices of developed countries to the specific conditions of Uzbekistan will be highly beneficial.

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